

ASSESSMENT OF THE IMMUNE STATUS IN CERVICAL DISEASES ASSOCIATED WITH HUMAN PAPILLOMAVIRUS

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In recent years, there has been a tendency in many countries of the world to increase the incidence of papillomavirus infection caused by the human papillomavirus (HPV). Despite the existing treatment methods, the problem of papillomavirus infection resistance to ongoing therapy is relevant. Squamous intraepithelial lesions of the cervix occupy a leading position in the structure of gynecological pathology among women of reproductive age [1,2].

The aim of the study was to develop prognostic criteria for cervical diseases associated with HPV in women of fertile age.

Materials and methods: 135 women were examined. Of these:

- 45-patients were with papillomavirus associated cervical diseases (PVAC) (group 1),
- 45- women with PVAC with transformation into oncopathology (group 2),
- 45 healthy women of fertile age (without the presence of oncogenic HPV types, clinical, cytological and colposcopic changes in the cervix), (group 3).

The average age of women in the 1st group was 33.9 ± 1.3 years, in the 2nd group- 44.1 ± 1.42 years and in the 3rd group- 38.9 ± 1.10 years.

All women underwent general laboratory, biochemical, immunological, virological, colposcopic and functional studies.

Results and discussion. As a result of the study of cytokines in the blood serum of patients of the examined groups, an increase in MCP-1, IL-6, TNF- α , TGF- 2β and VEGF-A was found in patients with papillomovirus associated cervical diseases (PVACD) of the 1st and 2nd groups.

The assessment of the chemotaxis process in patients selected for the study showed an increase in the level of MCP-1 in patients of group 1 by 1.36 times (315.2 ± 34.1 pg/ml), by 1.3 times in patients of group 2 (301.4 ± 20.2 pg/ml) compared to the control- 231.2 ± 17.35 pg/ml, which confirms the presence of an acute inflammatory process and activation of macrophages. The obtained result indicates activation and/or exacerbation of chronic cervical pathology.

There is an increase in the level of IL-6 in group 2 patients by 5.5 times, TNF-a by 7.8 times, an increase in the concentration of TGF- $\beta 2$ in the blood by 148.4 times, an increase in VEGF by 3.32 times, and there is also a tendency to decrease IGF levels to 89.8 ± 4.87 pg/ml, against control- 96.2 ± 2.08 pg/ml.

As a result of apoptosis and cell death, the cervical tissue disintegrates and deconstructs, which is confirmed paraclinically by the level of TNF- α in the blood serum. Studies have shown an increase in its level in patients of both groups: to 65.2 ± 3.87 pg/ml in group 1, and in group 2 to 63.9 ± 3.36 pg/ml versus control- 8.1 ± 0.81 pg/ml ($p < 0.001$). The results obtained obviously prove the disintegration of tissue at the level of cervical tissue with transformation into cervical cancer.

In our studies in patients with PVACD in women of reproductive age, an increase in the concentration of TGF- β_2 in the blood was found to 22.0 ± 0.77 ppg/ml in patients of group 1, to 474.9 ± 47.89 ppg/ml in patients of group 2, against control -3.2 ± 0.39 ppg/ml ($P < 0.001$).

TGF β has been proven to block the activation of lymphocytes and macrophages, as well as initiate apoptosis in most cell types. Consequently, TGF β causes cell apoptosis. Judging by the level of TGF- β_2 in the blood, it is possible to predict the state of the body's immune response.

The analysis of IGF levels showed a decrease of 1.23 times in patients of group 1 (123.0 ± 2.03 ng/ml), and a tendency to decrease it to 89.8 ± 4.87 ng/ml in patients of group 2, compared with the values of the control group- 96.2 ± 2.08 ng/ml ($P < 0.01$).

Conclusion

An increase in MCP-1, IL-6, TNF- α , TGF- 2β and VEGF-A was found in women with PVACD. Women with transformation into oncopathology have a high increase in the concentration of growth factors that regulate the processes of angiogenesis and hematopoiesis. At the same time, against the background of a decrease in the protective reparative processes of vascular wall restoration, there is a high risk of stimulation of growth and proliferation of cervical tissue.

References:

1. Datta N.R., Kumar P., Singh S., Gupta D., Srivastava A., Dhole T.N. Does pretreatment human papillomavirus (HPV) titers predict radiation response and survival outcomes in cancer cervix? A pilot study. *Gynecol. Oncol.*, 2016, no. 103, pp. 100–105. doi: 10.1016/j.ygyno.2016.01.058
2. Fakhry C., Westra W.H., Li S., Cmelak A., Ridge J.A., Pinto H., Forastiere A., Gillison M.L. Improved survival of patients with human papillomavirus-positive head and neck squamous cell carcinoma in a prospective clinical trial. *J. Natl. Cancer Inst.*, 2018, no. 100, pp. 261–269. doi: 10.1093/jnci/djn011

